

Deliverable 8.1

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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1 H2020's Open Research Data Pilot

A novelty in Horizon 2020 is the Open Research Data Pilot which aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by projects. The legal requirements for projects participating in this pilot are contained in the Article 29.3 of the Grant Agreement.

The scope of the pilot is anchored in the Work Programmes. For the 2016-2017 Work Programme, the areas of Horizon 2020 participating in the Open Research Data Pilot include “Societal Challenge: Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bioeconomy”. Therefore, **ATLAS is part of H2020's Open Access Research Data Pilot and must develop a Data Management Plan (DMP) specifying how we will improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by the project. Furthermore, all partners of ATLAS must comply with Article 29 of the Grant Agreement.**

The Pilot on Open Research Data will be monitored throughout Horizon 2020 with a view to further developing EC policy on open research. **ATLAS intends to actively contribute to this development by implementing innovative and effective open science practices.**

2 H2020's Data Management Plan (DMP)

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy with regard to all data sets that will be generated by the project. The DMP is not a fixed document, but evolves during the lifespan of the project. The DMP should address the points below on a data set by data set basis and should reflect the current status of reflection within the consortium about the data that will be produced (source: European Commission DGRI. 2016. Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020).

- **Data set reference and name** - Identifier for the data set to be produced.
- **Data set description** - Description of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin (in case it is collected), nature and scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse.
- **Standards and metadata** - Reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created.
- **Data sharing** - Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing

and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).

- **Archiving and preservation** (including storage and backup) - Description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

3 ATLAS' Grant Agreement - Article 29 – Dissemination of results, open access and visibility of EU funding

The Data Management Plan and Open Science Policy of project ATLAS specifically address Article 29 of the Grant agreement. It is included here as a key reference.

29.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1) — need to formally notify the Agency before dissemination takes place.

29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- a) *as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.*
- b) *ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:*
 - i. *on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or*
 - ii. *within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.*
- c) *ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication. The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:*
 - i. *the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;*
 - ii. *the name of the action, acronym and grant number;*
 - iii. *the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and*
 - iv. *a persistent identifier.*

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:

- a) *deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge — the following:*
 - i. *the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible;*
 - ii. *other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan';*
- b) *provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply. As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective, as described in Annex 1, would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.*

29.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- a) display the EU emblem and*
- b) include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 678760”.*

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

29.5 Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

29.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

4 ATLAS’ Data Management Plan (DMP)

ATLAS will generate diverse research outputs, including data, software and scientific articles about physical oceanography, biogeochemistry, visual surveys of biodiversity, biological rates and traits measurements, genomic analyses, socio-economic metrics, and spatial planning. This diversity requires an ambitious data management plan, building on existing open science resources that are interoperable and trusted. The key to implementing ATLAS’ Data Management Plan is to appoint an information specialist (UniHB) with experience in marine science who will act as facilitator between ATLAS partners and six open science resources:

- ENA, the European Nucleotides Archive (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>)
- PANGAEA, Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science (<http://www.pangaea.de>)
- EuBI, Euro-BioImaging (<http://www.eurobioimaging.eu/>)
- ZENODO, EU-funded open access digital repository (<https://zenodo.org>)
- OpenAIRE, H2020’s research monitoring infrastructure (<https://www.openaire.eu>)
- EMODnet, the European Marine Observation and Data Network (<http://www.EMODnet.eu>)

In compliance with H2020's Open Research Data Pilot, these resources (i.e. ENA, PANGAEA, EuBI) ensure that **data sets are archived and preserved**, using a **reference and name** (i.e. authors, year, title, DOI or accession number), a **description** (i.e. targeted use, geolocation, methods, link to related articles), and community **standards and metadata** (i.e. parameters semantic, formats, units, and use of ontologies and registries). Unless authors request that data be embargoed (see ATLAS' Open Science Policy below), data sets archived at ENA, PANGAEA, EuBI are available freely in open access (see Task 8.3 below). Moreover, data sharing and reporting to the EC is maximised by disseminating metadata to OpenAIRE and EMODnet (see Tasks 8.4 & 8.5 below). A **list of data and metadata expected from ATLAS' research activities** is provided in Appendix I, based on previous EU projects that conducted similar studies, i.e. HERMES, HERMIONE and CoralFISH. The Data Management Plan of ATLAS is coordinated by Work Package 8, and is articulated around five key objectives/tasks:

Task 8.1 Engage ATLAS partners in H2020's Open Research Data Pilot

This task essentially consists in effectively communicating the founding principles and implementation steps of ATLAS' DMP and Open Science Policy to all partners of the project. This will be achieved by personal communication between partners and the information specialist (UniHB) during the entire life cycle of the project. Furthermore, ATLAS will engage in the development of community-oriented services that help deposit, link and enrich research outputs as part of OpenAIRE-Connect.

Task 8.2 Assemble relevant research outputs from past EU-funded and nationally-funded efforts

This task will assemble a collection of research outputs (e.g. literature, data, maps and model outputs) available in open access from past and on-going research initiatives that are relevant to Atlantic-ecosystem-based research. These include projects funded under FP6 (HERMES), FP7 (HERMIONE, CoralFISH, THOR, EURO-BASIN, FixO3) and H2020 (AtlantOS and SponGES), and initiatives funded in the USA (NOAA) and Canada (DFO). This task will establish a list of data and metadata expected from ATLAS' research activities (see Appendix I).

Task 8.3 Safeguard and publish ATLAS' research outputs in open access

Research articles will be published in peer-reviewed journals and other digital material (other than data) will be deposited at ZENODO. Nucleotides data, imaging data, and environmental data (including bathymetry, physics, chemistry and biology) will be deposited in the selected data archives, i.e. European Nucleotides Archive (ENA), Euro-BiolImaging (EuBI) and PANGAEA, respectively.

There are two main routes towards open access to literature and data publications:

- **Gold open access (open access publishing)** means that data sets or articles are immediately provided in open access by the publisher. The business model of most journal publishers is shifting the payment of publication costs away from readers (subscription charges) towards the authors (Article Processing Charges, APCs). These costs can usually be borne by the university or research institute to which the researcher is affiliated, or to the funding agency supporting the research. ATLAS partners are strongly encouraged to use their institutional or ATLAS funds to publish research articles in Gold Open Access. Publishing data at ENA, EuBI and PANGAEA also follows gold open access but the cost model is different. ENA and EuBI are European Infrastructures and therefore offer their service free of charge to authors. The publication costs of data sets at PANGAEA are included in the budget of ATLAS' UniHB partner. The information specialist (UniHB) will assist ATLAS' partners in publishing their data in open access.
- **Green open access (self-archiving)** means that data sets or articles are archived (deposited) for free by the author in an online repository. In the case of articles submitted to a non-open access journal, a final, peer-reviewed and proofed-read version can be deposited in Green Open Access. Some journal publishers request that open access be granted only after an embargo period has elapsed. Research outputs that are published in non-open access by ATLAS partners will be deposited at ZENODO. The information specialist (UniHB) will assist ATLAS' partners in publishing their data in open access.

Task 8.4 Monitor and report on ATLAS research outputs using OpenAIRE (M6-M48)

This will be achieved by actively monitoring data and literature publications from ATLAS partners using services from DataCite and Thompson Reuters, and by maintaining close communication with ENA, EuBI, PANGAEA and ZENODO. The information specialist (UniHB) will ensure that all research outputs (e.g. literature, data, maps and model outputs) from ATLAS are cross-linked and monitored by OpenAIRE. The information specialist (UniHB) will also assist ATLAS partners in engaging and using OpenAIRE-Connect. OpenAIRE will be used to report on research outputs from the project (<https://www.openaire.eu/project/ATLAS>). The following deliverables will also provide regular updates on ATLAS research outputs:

- D8.2 18-month progress report on ATLAS data integration in EMODnet
- D8.3 36-month progress report on ATLAS data integration in EMODnet
- D8.4 42-month Synthesis of ATLAS research outputs available in open access

Task 8.5 Transfer ATLAS research outputs to science and industry stakeholders using EMODnet

ATLAS research outputs (i.e. data and linked journal publications) available in open access will be transferred to EMODnet, using the interoperability protocols specified by the different EMODnet thematic nodes (e.g. bathymetry, chemistry and biology).

5 ATLAS' Open Science Policy

The Open Science Policy of ATLAS provides a clear workflow for safeguarding and sharing research outputs for reuse by researchers, industry stakeholders and policy makers. Research outputs include **preliminary (draft)** and **final versions** of data sets, articles, cruise summary reports, presentations, posters, code, and software. In compliance with Article 29 of the Grant Agreement, and following best practices described in the Data Management Plan, individuals who are involved in ATLAS activities will:

- register at ORCID (<http://orcid.org/>) and communicate their ORCID ID to the ATLAS project office (katherine.simpson@ed.ac.uk);
- ensure that 45 days prior to submitting research output for publication (e.g. submitting a manuscript to a scientific journal), a **preliminary (draft) version** is sent to the ATLAS project office (Katherine Simpson, katherine.simpson@ed.ac.uk and Murray Roberts, murray.roberts@ed.ac.uk), indicating where it will be submitted. The draft can consist of the complete research output (e.g. full manuscript), or include at minimum the title, authors and abstract. The project office will make sure that the EC is properly acknowledged in the research output and will send the authors a contribution number. The draft will be placed on the password protected area of the eu-atlas website and all ATLAS partners will be informed by email by the Project Office. Comments about the draft research output should be sent directly to the authors and any concerns should be raised with the project coordinator. Unless issues have been raised during a period of 30 days, it is considered that all partners have read the research output and agree with its content.
- ensure that the **final version** of Cruise Summary Reports (CSRs) are deposited in open access at ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=atlas>) no later than three months after the cruise. CSRs should include a list of sampling activities, measured parameters and contact details of principal investigators for each parameter;
- ensure that the **final version** of all other research outputs are deposited at ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=atlas>) as soon as possible and no later than three months after their production. Access to these research outputs can be restricted;
- ensure that research outputs are made available preferably in gold open access (or a least green open access) as soon as possible and at the latest six months after publication; twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities; twenty-four months in the case of unpublished data that are part of a research thesis;

- ensure that data supporting any type of research output are deposited in a trusted archive (see DMP Section 4) and that research outputs and data sets are cross-referencing each other (i.e. linked publication);

For any question or assistance regarding the dissemination and exploitation of:

- **preliminary (draft) versions** of your research outputs, please contact Katherine Simpson (katherine.simpson@ed.ac.uk);
- **final versions of your research outputs**, or regarding Open Science in general, please contact Stéphane Pesant (spesant@marum.de);
- **final versions of public outreach materials**, please contact Claudia Junge (claudia@aquatt.ie), and consult the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (DEP) of ATLAS (<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.167409>).

6 Appendix I – Parameters expected from research activities of ATLAS

The following table was compiled from data sets published from three previous European projects that were similar in scope to ATLAS, i.e. HERMES, HERMIONE and CoralFISH. We therefore expect that the parameters listed in this table will either be measured during field and experimental campaigns organised by or in collaboration with ATLAS partners, or re-used from already published data sets.

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
amount concentration of biological entity per unit mass of environmental entity	Bacteria, abundance per unit sediment mass	10**6 #/g
amount concentration of biological entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Prokaryotes, abundance as single cells; Bacteria, abundance	10**9 #/cm**3
amount concentration of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Acid volatile sulphides; Chromium reducible sulphides; Iron ascorbic acid extraction; Iron dithionite extraction; Ammonium; Carbon, inorganic, dissolved; Carbon, organic, dissolved; Iron, total, dissolved; Nitrate; Nitrite; Nitrogen, total dissolved; Oxygen; Phosphate; Silicate; Sulfite; Sulphide; Thiosulphate; Concentration; Heptasulphide; Hexasulphide; Iron 2+; Pentasulphide; Polythionate; Tetrasulphide; Trisulphide; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water cyanolysis; Zero valent sulphur, in pore water ZnCl2 extraction; Sulphur, elemental; Alkalinity, total; Chloride; Sulphate; Phospholipids; Adenylates, total	µmol/cm**3; µmol/l; µmol/ml; mmol(eq)/l; mmol/l; nmol/ml; pmol/cm**3
amount rate of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	Methane flux; Oxygen flux, sediment oxygen demand; Methane, oxidation rate, anaerobic	mmol/m**2/day

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
amount rate of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Esterase activity per sediment volume	nmol/ml/h
mass concentration of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	Carbon, organic, particulate per area, fraction; Carbon, total particulate; Carbon, total particulate, fraction; Nitrogen, organic, particulate; Nitrogen, organic, particulate, fraction; Carbon, organic, particulate per area; Particle concentration, resuspendable; Marine litter, mass per area	g/m**2; kg/km**2

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
mass concentration of chemical entity per unit mass of environmental entity	<p>Amino acid, hydrolysable per unit sediment mass; Amino acids per unit sediment mass; Carbohydrates, acid soluble; Carbohydrates, NaOH soluble; Carbohydrates, total; Lipids, total; Proteins, total; Acenaphthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthylene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Acenaphthylene, per unit mass organic carbon; alpha-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; alpha-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)pyrene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(a)pyrene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(b)fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(b)fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(g,h,i)perylene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(g,h,i)perylene, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(k)fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Benz(k)fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Chrysene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Chrysene, per unit mass organic carbon; Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluoranthene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluoranthene, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluorene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Fluorene, per unit mass organic carbon; gamma-Hexachlorocyclohexane, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; gamma-Hexachlorocyclohexane, per unit mass organic carbon; Hexachlorobenzene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Hexachlorobenzene, per unit mass organic carbon; Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene, per unit mass organic carbon; Naphthalene, fraction, per unit mass organic carbon; Naphthalene, per unit mass organic carbon; ortho,para-Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane, fraction, per unit mass organic C;</p>	μg/g; mg/kg; ng/kg

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
mass concentration of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Chloroplastic pigment equivalents per area; Chloroplastic pigment equivalents per volume; Chlorophyll a; Chlorophyll pigment equivalents; Phaeopigments; Carbon, organic, total per volume; Density, sigma, in situ; Density, sigma2000; Density, sigma-theta (0); Density, mass density; Protein, readily soluble per sediment volume	$\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^{**3}$; $\mu\text{g}/\text{l}$; kg/m^{**3} ; $\text{mg}/\text{cm}^{**3}$
mass concentration of chemical entity; biological entity per unit area of environmental entity	Bacteria, biomass as carbon; Benthos, biomass as carbon; Biomass as carbon; Copepoda, biomass as carbon; Meiofauna, biomass as carbon; Nematoda, biomass as carbon; Polychaeta, biomass as carbon	$\mu\text{g}/10 \text{ cm}^{**2}$; mg/m^{**2}
mass of biological entity	Amblyraja radiata, mass; Anarhichas denticulatus, mass; Anarhichas lupus, mass; Brosme brosme, mass; Chimaera monstrosa, mass; Etmopterus spinax, mass; Gadus morhua, mass; Galeus melastomus, mass; Gorgonacea, mass; Lithodes maja, mass; Lophelia pertusa, mass; Melanogrammus aeglefinus, mass; Molva molva, mass; Pollachius virens, mass; Porifera, mass; Rajella fyllae, mass; Sebastes norvegicus, mass	kg
mass rate of chemical entity per unit area of environmental entity	24-Ethylcholest-5-en-3beta-ol flux; 24-Methylcholest-5-en-3beta-ol flux; 24-Methylcholesta-5,22E-dien-3beta-ol flux; all-cis-4,7,10,13,16,19-Docosahexaenoic acid flux; all-cis-5,8,11,14,17-Icosapentaenoic acid flux; all-cis-6,9,12,15-Octadecatetraenoic acid flux; Cholesta-5-en-3beta-ol flux; cis-11-Hexadecenoic acid flux; cis-9-Hexadecenoic acid flux; Lipids flux; Biogenic flux; Biopolymeric carbon flux; Calcium carbonate flux; Carbohydrate flux; Carbon, inorganic, particulate flux per day; Carbon, organic, particulate flux per day; Flux of total mass; Lithogenic flux per day; Nitrogen, organic, particulate flux per day; Nitrogen, particulate flux; Opal flux; Organic matter flux; Protein total flux; Silica, particulate flux per day; Silicon, particulate flux; Total mass flux per day	$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^{**2}/\text{day}$; $\text{mg}/\text{m}^{**2}/\text{day}$

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
mass rate of chemical entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Sulphate reduction rate; Methane, oxidation rate	nmol/cm**3/day
mass rate of chemical entity; biological entity per unit volume of environmental entity	Bacterial biomass production of carbon	ng/l/h
metadata	Buildup; Taxa analyzed; Replicates; Seismic line; Mesh size; Sample surface; Time, incubation; Duration, number of days; Signal strength; Pressure, water; Current direction; Current meter, pitch; Current meter, roll; Current meter, tilt; Course; Direction; Duration; File size; Depth, bottom/max; Depth, top/min; DEPTH, sediment/rock; DEPTH, water; Depth, bathymetric; Height above sea floor/altitude; Recovery; Taxon/taxa; Position; Description; Experimental treatment; Area/locality; Comment; Date/time end; Date/time start; Device type; Event; File name; Gear; Latitude 2; Longitude 2; Parameter; Reference of data; Reference/source; Sample code/label; Sample comment; Split; DATE/TIME; LATITUDE; LONGITUDE; ORDINAL NUMBER; Sorting; Species; Core; File format; Log info; Number; Profile; Sample ID; Sample, optional label/labor no; Shoot point; Site; Treatment; Type; Uniform resource locator/link to file; Uniform resource locator/link to graphic; Uniform resource locator/link to image; Uniform resource locator/link to metadata file; Uniform resource locator/link to movie; Uniform resource locator/link to raw data file; Uniform resource locator/link to sgy data file; Uniform resource locator/link to thumbnail; Cruise/expedition; Depth, bathymetric, maximum; Depth, bathymetric, minimum; ELEVATION; Feature; Filter; Hooks; Identification; Legibility; Location; Method comment; Seastate label; Section; Species code; Status	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
non-parametric quality of biological entity	Sex; Stage	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity	Coral Status; Food; Habitat; Substrate type; Morphology	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity per unit biological entity	Coral; <i>Amblyraja radiata</i> ; <i>Anarhichas denticulatus</i> ; <i>Anarhichas lupus</i> ; <i>Brosme brosme</i> ; <i>Chimaera monstrosa</i> ; <i>Clupea harengus</i> abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; <i>Etmopterus spinax</i> ; Fish; <i>Gadus morhua</i> ; <i>Gorgonacea</i> ; <i>Lithodes maja</i> ; <i>Lophelia pertusa</i> ; <i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i> ; <i>Molva molva</i> ; <i>Pollachius virens</i> ; <i>Rajella fyllae</i> ; <i>Sebastes norvegicus</i> ; Sponge	
non-parametric quality of environmental entity per unit anthropogenic entity	Marine litter, clinker; Marine litter, fabric; Marine litter, fishing net; Marine litter, glass; Marine litter, hard plastic; Marine litter, long line; Marine litter, metal; Marine litter, oil drum; Marine litter, soft plastic	
parametric quality of environmental entity	Food index; Porosity; Species richness; Dauwe index; Diversity; Equitability; Shannon index of diversity	
parametric quality of environmental entity per unit biological entity	Nematoda, trophic diversity; Mesopelagic fish abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; <i>Micromesistius poutassou</i> abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; Plankton abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient; <i>Pollachius virens</i> abundance as Nautical Area Scattering Coefficient	
parametric quality of physical entity	Temperature, in rock/sediment; Temperature, water; Temperature, water, potential; Fluorescence; Turbidity; Echo backscatter; Turbidity (Formazin Turbidity Unit); Conductivity; Oxidation reduction (RedOx) potential; pH; Salinity; Attenuation, optical beam transmission; Humidity, relative; Pressure, atmospheric; Radiation, photosynthetically active; Temperature, air; Wind direction	degC; arbitrary units; dB; mS/cm; mV

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
ratio of biological entity per unit biological entity	<p>Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1 archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1-350 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a-647 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2a,b; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-2c; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3; Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3 archaea, targeted with Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-3-1249 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Archaea, Anaerobic methanotrophic archaea-1; Archaea, GEG; Archaea, GoM Arc I; Archaea, MBG-B; Archaea, MBG-D; Archaea, targeted with ARCH915 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Methanomicrobiales; Methanosaeta related Methanosarcinales; Methanosarcinales, unaffiliated; Acidobacteria; Acrobacter spp., targeted with ARC94 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Actinobacteria; Alphaproteobacteria; Bacteria; Bacteria, JS1; Bacteria, OP11; Bacteria, OP8; Bacteria, targeted with EUB338(I-III) oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Bacteria, TG1; Bacteria, unaffiliated; Bacteria, WS2; Bacteria, WS3; Bacteroidetes; Betaproteobacteria; Chlorobi; Chloroflexi; Deferribacteres; Delta-Proteobacteria; Desulfusarcina/Desulfococcus, targeted with DSS658 oligonucleotide FISH-probe; Epsilonproteobacteria; Firmicutes; Fusobacteria; Gammaproteobacteria; Planctomycetes; Spirochaetes; Meiofauna; Foraminifera, benthic hyaline; Adelosina spp.; Ammolagena clavata; Ammonia beccarii; Amphicoryna scalaris; Angulogerina angulosa; Articulina tubulosa; Asterigerinata mamilla; Astrononion stelligerum; Bigenerina nodosaria; Biloculinella depressa; Biloculinella inflata; Biloculinella labiata; Bolivina pseudoplicata; Bolivina pseudopunctata; Brizalina alata; Brizalina albatrossi; Brizalina dilatata; Brizalina subaenariensis; Bulimina aculeata; Bulimina costata; Bulimina elongata; Bulimina marginata; Bulimina striata mexicana; Cassidulina laevigata; Cassidulina oblonga; Cassidulinoides bradyi; Chilostomella oolina; Cibicides lobatulus; Cibicides spp.; Cibicidoides pachyderma; Cibicidoides spp.; Cornuspira involvens; Dentalina albatrossi; Dentalina spp.; Discammina compressa; Discanomalina semipunctata; Discorbinella bertheloti; Discorbis spp.; Elphidium spp.; Epistominella rugosa; Fissurina spp.; Fursenkoina cf. acuta; Fursenkoina mexicana; Gavelinopsis praegeri; Glandulina spp.; Globobulimina affinis; Globobulimina pseudospinescens; Globobulimina spp.; Glomospira charoides; Guttulina cf. communis; Gyroidinoides neosoldanii; Gyroidinoides orbicularis; Gyroidinoides umbonatus; Haynesina spp.; High oxygen indicators; Hoeglundina elegans; Hyaline balthica; Laevidentalina flexuosa; Lagena spp.; Lenticulina calcar; Lenticulina cultrata; Lenticulina orbicularis; Lenticulina</p>	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
	<p>spp.; Low oxygen indicators; Marginulina spp.; Marginulinopsis spp.; Melonis barleeanus; Miliolinella spp.; Miliolinella subrotunda; Neoconorbina terquemi; Neolenticulina peregrina; Nonion asterizans; Nonion depressulum; Nonionella turgida; Nummuloculina contraria; Oolina spp.; Paracassidulina minuta; Patellina corrugata; Placopsilina sp.; Planorbulina mediterraneensis; Planulina ariminensis; Polymorphina spp.; Pseudoclavulina crustata; Pseudotriloculina laevigata; Pseudotriloculina oblonga; Pullenia bulloides; Pullenia salisburyi; Pullenia subcarinata; Pyrgo cf. murrhina; Pyrgo comata; Pyrgo elongata; Pyrgo inornata; Pyrgo spp.; Pyrgoella sphaera; Quinqueloculina laevigata; Quinqueloculina milletti; Quinqueloculina padana; Quinqueloculina seminula; Quinqueloculina spp.; Quinqueloculina venusta; Quinqueloculina viennensis; Repmanina charoides; Reussella spinulosa; Rhabdammina sp.; Robertinoides translucens; Rosalina bradyi; Rosalina spp.; Rotamorphina involuta; Sigmoidina costata; Sigmoidina sigmoidea; Sigmoidinita tenuis; Sigmoidinopsis schlumbergeri; Siphonaperta aspera; Siphonina reticulata; Siphonotextularia heterostoma; Sphaeroidina bulloides; Spiroloculina sp.; Spiroplectinella sagittula; Textularia agglutinans; Textularia pala; Triloculina spp.; Triloculina tricarinata; Uvigerina mediterranea; Uvigerina peregrina; Uvigerina proboscidea; Valvulinaria bradyana</p>	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
ratio of chemical entity per unit chemical entity	Alanine; alpha-aminobutyric acid; Arginine; Asparagine; beta-Alanine; gamma-Aminobutyric acid; Glutamine; Glycine; Histidine; Isoleucine; Leucine; Lysine; Methionine; Ornithine; Phenylalanine; Serine; Threonine; Tyrosine; Valine; Nitrogen, organic, fraction; Oxygen, saturation; Methane; Organic matter; Ethane; n-Butane; Propane; Isobutane; Hydrate; Water content of wet mass; Aluminium; Calcium; Calcium carbonate; Carbon, inorganic, total; Carbon, organic, fraction; Carbon, organic, particulate; Carbon, organic, total; Carbon, total; Iron; Magnesium; Nitrogen, organic; Nitrogen, total; Opal, biogenic silica; Silicon; Sulphur, total; Lithogenic material; Volcanic glass, acidic; delta 15N; delta 15N, particulate organic nitrogen; delta 234 Uranium; Acid volatile sulphides isotopes; Chromium reducible sulphides isotopes; delta 13C; delta 13C, adjusted/corrected; delta 13C, organic carbon; delta 13C, particulate organic carbon; C1/C2 hydrocarbon ratio; C1/C2+ hydrocarbon ratio; C1/C3 hydrocarbon ratio; Lead 206/Lead 207; Lead 208/Lead 206 ratio; Neodymium 143/Neodymium 144; Strontium 87/Strontium 86 ratio; epsilon-Neodymium (0); Thorium 230/Thorium 232 ratio; Thorium 230/Uranium 234 ratio; Uranium 234/Uranium 238 activity ratio; Uranium 238/Thorium 232 ratio; Calcium/(Calcium+Iron) ratio; Carbon/Nitrogen ratio; Carbon/Sulphur ratio; Nitrogen/Carbon ratio	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
unit concentration of biological entity per unit area of environmental entity	Eumeiofauna; Meiofauna, abundance; Pseudomeiofauna; Abundance per area; Benthos, other; Copepoda indeterminata; Meiofauna, abundance of foraminifera; Meiofauna, abundance of harpacticoida; Meiofauna, abundance of metazoa; Cladocera; Foraminifera, benthic; Lysianassidae; Scaphopoda; Anomonema; Chitwoodia; Comesomoides; Cricolaimus; Cylicolaimus; Demonema; Desmocolex; Diplolaimelloides; Echinodesmodora; Endeolophos; Eubostrichus; Eudiplogaster; Gairleanema; Gomphionchus; Gonionchus; Kraspedonema; Leptonemella; Metadasynemoides; Monoposthia; Morlaixia; Odontophoroides; Omicronema; Parachromadorita; Paradesmodora; Parallelocoilas; Paranticoma; Perspiria; Polysigma; Pontonema; Prochromadora; Psammonema; Pseudocella; Steineridora; Trichotheristus; Valvaelaimus; Cirratulidae; Maldanidae; Paramphinome sp.; Spionidae; Acari; Amphimonhystrella bullacauda; Antarcticonema; Asellota; Bathyepsilonema; Calanoidea; Cheironchus; Ciliata; Comesoma; Cyatholaimus; Deontolaimus; Desmodora pilosa; Desmodoroidea; Desmolorenzenia; Desmotricoma; Dorylaimopsis; Ethmolaimidae; Goniadidae; Greeffiellinae; Greeffiellopsis; Halanonchus; Hesionidae; Ixonema; Karkinochromadora; Lacydoniidae; Lumbrineridae; Metacomesoma; Metacylicolaimus; Monhysterina; Nannolaimoides; Nephtyidae; Nicascolaimus; Notochaetosoma; Nyctonema; Opheliidae; Ophiuroidea; Pandolaimus; Paraethmolaimus; Paraonidae; Parapinnanema; Pareudesmoscolex; Phoxocephalidae; Phyllodocidae; Pilargidae; Prochaetosoma; Pseudolella; Quadricoma; Sabatieria bitumen; Sabatieria conicauda; Sabatieria demani; Sabatieria lawsi; Sabatieria ornata; Sabatieria propisinna; Sabatieria punctata; Sabatieria stekhoveni; Sabatieria vasicola; Sipuncula; Synonchium; Tanaoidea; Tarvaia; Tetrapturus; Thoracostomopsis; Amphinomidae; Capitellidae; Glyceridae; Terebellidae; Virus; Carrier crab; Copepoda; Crab; Edible crab; Galeus melastomus; Gastrotricha; Kinorhyncha; Nematoda genus sp.; Number of clones; Number of individuals; Phylotype number; Shrimps; Small grenadier; Spinder crab; Squat lobster; Swimmer crab; Foraminifera, benthic agglutinated; Foraminifera, benthic agglutinated indeterminata; Foraminifera, benthic calcareous; Foraminifera, benthic perforates indeterminata; Foraminifera, chitineous; Insects, total counts; Ostracoda; Ameira; Ameirinae; Ameiropsis; Amphiascoidea; Amphiascus; Archesola; Argestes; Argestidae; Atergopedia; Bathycamptus; Bodinia; Bradya; Bradyellopsis; Canthocamptidae; Cletodes; Cyclopoida; Cyllindronannopus; Diarthrodella; Dizahavia; Ectinosoma; Ectinosomatidae; Enhydrosoma; Eurycletodes; Filexilia; Fultonia; Halectinosoma; Halophytophilus; Haloschizopera; Hastigerella; Heterolaophonte;	#; #/10 cm**2; #/m**2

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
	Idomene; Idyanthe; Idyanthidae; Idyella; Klieosoma; Kliopsyllus; Laophonte; Laophontodes; Leptomesochra; Leptopsyllus; Lineosoma; Lobopleura; Malacopsyllus; Marsteinia; Mesochra; Mesocletodes; Metahuntemannia; Microsetella; Misophrioida; Nematovorax; Neobryidae; Novocriidae; Parameiopsis; Paramesochra; Paramesochridae; Parapseudoleptomesochra; Peltobrya; Perissocope; Poecilostomatoida; Pseudameira; Pseudobrya; Pseudomesochra; Pseudotachidiinae; Rhyncholagena; Rhynchothalestris; Robertgurneya; Sagamiella; Sarsameira; Scottopsyllus; Sigmatidium; Siphonostomatoida; Stenocopia; Talpina; Tegastes; Tetragonicepsidae; Xylora; Zosime; Dendrophyllia cornigera; Desmophylum; Lophelia; Madrepora oculata; Centrophorus squamosus; Helicolenus dactylopterus dactylopterus; Hexanchus griseus; Lepidion eques; Lopheous piscatorius; Mora moro; Phycis blennoides; Synaphobranchus kaupi; Dendrophyllia; Madrepora; Actinonema; Adoncholaimus; Aegialoalaimidae; Amphimonhystera; Anticyathus; Aponema; Araeolaimus; Ascolaimus; Astomonema; Bathynox; Benthimermithidae; Bodonema; Bolbolaimus; Calligyru; Catanema; Cephalanticoma; Ceramonema; Chaetonema; Choanolaimus; Chromadorella; Chromadoridae; Cobbia; Comesa; Comesomatidae; Coninckia; Cyatholaimidae; Dasyneimoides; Desmodorella; Desmodoridae; Didelta; Diodontolaimus; Diplolaimella; Diplopeltidae; Diplopeltis; Disconema; Dolicholaimus; Doliolaimus; Draconema; Elzalia; Enchelidiidae; Enopliinae; Enoploides; Enoplus; Epacanthion; Euchromadora; Eurystomina; Filoncholaimus; Gammanema; Glochinema; Gnomoxyala; Graphonema; Greeffiella; Halichoanolaimus; Haliplectus; Halomonhystera; Hapalonus; Hopperia; Hypodontolaimus; Intasia; Laimella; Latronema; Leptosomatium; Linhomoeidae; Linhomoeus; Litinium; Longicyatholaimus; Megadesmolaimus; Mesacanthion; Mesacanthoides; Metachromadora; Metacyatholaimus; Metadasynemella; Metaparoncholaimus; Metasphaerolaimus; Metoncholaimus; Micoletzkyia; Microlaimidae; Minolaimus; Monhystera; Monhysteridae; Nannolaimus; Nemanema; Neochromadora; Neotonchus; Noffsingeria; Odontanticoma; Odontophora; Oncholaimellus; Oncholaimidae; Oncholaimus; Paracomesoma; Paralongicyatholaimus; Paramesonchium; Paramicrolaimus; Paramonhystera; Pararaeolaimus; Parasphaerolaimus; Parastomonema; Paratricoma; Pareurystomina; Parodontophora; Phanoderma; Phanodermatidae; Phanodermopsis; Pierrickia; Platycoma; Platycomopsis; Praeacanthonchus; Promonhystera; Prooncholaimus; Prototricoma; Pseudonchus; Pterygonema; Ptycholaimellus; Rhynchonema; Richtersia; Setoplectus; Setosabatieria; Siphonolaimus; Sphaerolaimidae; Spilophorella;	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
	<p>Spinodesmoscolex; Spirobolbolaimus; Steineria; Stephanolaimus; Stylotheristus; Symplocostoma; Synodontium; Synonchiella; Synonchus; Thalassironus; Trefusia; Trefusialaimus; Tripyloides; Trissonchulus; Trochamus; Xennella; Xyala; Acantholaimus; Acanthonchus; Aegialolaimus; Alaimella; Ammotheristus; Amphimonhystrella; Amphipoda; Anoplostoma; Anticoma; Antomicron; Aplacophora; Atrochromadora; Axonolaimus; Bathyeurystomina; Belbolla; Bivalvia; Calanoida; Calomicrolaimus; Calyptonema; Camacolaimus; Campylaimus; Cervonema; Chromadora; Chromadorina; Chromadorita; Chromaspirina; Cnidaria; Crenopharynx; Cricohalalaimus; Cumacea; Cyartonema; Dagda; Daptonema; Desmodora; Desmolaimus; Desmoscolecida; Desmoscolex; Dichromadora; Diplopeltoides; Diplopeltula; Draconematidae; Echinodermata; Eleutherolaimus; Enoplolaimus; Epsilonema; Ethmolaimus; Eumorpholaimus; Fenestrolaimus; Filitonchus; Gerlachius; Gnathostomulida; Halacarida; Halalaimus; Holothuroidea; Hydrozoa; Indeterminata; Innocuonema; Intoshia; Isopoda; Ledovitia; Leptolaimoides; Leptolaimus; Linhystera; Loricifera; Manganonema; Marylynnia; Metadesmolaimus; Metepsilonema; Meyersia; Microlaimus; Molgolaimus; Monhystrella; Nauplii; Nematoda; Oligochaeta; Oxyonchus; Oxystomina; Paracanthonchus; Paracyatholaimoides; Paracyatholaimus; Paralinhomoeus; Paramesacanthion; Paramonohystera; Polychaeta; Pomponema; Porifera; Priapulida; Procamacolaimus; Prochromadorella; Pselionema; Pseudochromadora; Retrotheristus; Rhabdocoma; Rhabdodemia; Rhips; Rotifera; Sabatieria; Sipunculida; Southerniella; Sphaerolaimus; Spiliphera; Spirinia; Stygodesmodora; Subsphaerolaimus; Syncarida; Synonema; Syringolaimus; Tanaidacea; Tantulocarida; Tardigrada; Terschellingia; Thalassoalaimus; Thalassomonhystera; Theristus; Tricoma; Trileptium; Turbellaria; Vasostoma; Viscosia; Wieseria; Xyalidae; Metalinhomoeus; Adercotryma sp.; Ammodiscus sp.; Bolivina sp.; Buliminella sp.; Discorbinellidae indeterminata; Epistominella sp.; Fissurina sp.; Ioannella sp.; Lagenammina sp.; Lagenammina sp.; Nodellum sp.; Oolina sp.; Reophax sp.; Triloculina sp.; Gastropoda; Harpacticoida</p>	

Category of parameters	Parameters	Units
volume of biological entity	Bacteria, cell biovolume; Bacteria, heterotrophic, cell biovolume	μm^3